

INFLUENCE OF TEACHER COMPETENCIES ON PROFESSIONAL SKILLS ACQUISITION OF OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT STUDENTS IN PUBLIC POLYTECHNICS IN OSUN STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252293>

Abstract

The study examined influence of teachers' competence on professional skills acquisition of Office Technology and Management students in public polytechnics in Osun State. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Two research questions guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 27 lecturers of OTM departments, Federal Polytechnic, Ede and Osun State Polytechnic, Iree, Osun State, Nigeria. The study used total enumeration; hence no sampling was made. Data was collected through questionnaire with internal consistency test yielding Cronbach alpha value of 0.82. Simple mean method was the tool used to analyze the research questions. The study found that level of teacher's competence is relatively high and that the competence level has positive influence on skill acquisition among OTM students in the polytechnics. Based on these findings, it was concluded that lecturers' level of competence in teaching OTM professional skills in public polytechnics is high, and that the level of competence has positive influence on skills acquisition of the students. It was therefore, recommended that OTM lecturers should explore other factors affecting professional skills acquisition of their students with a view to ensuring provision of high-quality products of the OTM programme.

Keywords: Teacher competencies, Teaching strategies, Skills acquisition, OTM students

Introduction

The acquisition of the professional skills is a means of increasing the productive power of any nations. Consequently, the Oyinloye and Oluwalola (2010) opined that the Nigerian society should recognize the fact that every citizen should be equipped to contribute effectively to the welfare of the country. The acquisition of such professional skills is important because when efficient and skilful hands are employed in any fields of human endeavours, high productivity is usually achieved. Economically, therefore, professional skills acquisition by OTM students will help to enrich the Nigerian society and, in this way, tend to facilitate economic development.

Office Technology and Management programme education is defined as that education that provides skills, knowledge and attitudes necessary for effective employment in secretarial and management occupations. Furthermore, Udo (2018) Office Technology and Management is a comprehensive activity-based educational programme that is concerned with the acquisition of office technology and management skills, understandings, attitudes, work habits and competencies that are requisite to success in secretarial and office management occupations. According to Enang and Okute (2019), skill acquisition

for managing the electronic-driven office should cover not only skills in shorthand and typewriting, but also skills in usage of modern technologies. Acquisition of skills in ICT-based courses and use of various modern office machines and appliances is thus a necessity. In the realization of this, OTM programme was designed in a way that all students offered all core courses in the first two years to have general knowledge of the content of OTM professional skills. This is to achieve one of the objectives of National Commission on Colleges of Education which states that OTM graduates are to be equipped with the right skills that will enable them to engage in the world of work as well as for self-employment.

In order to achieve this objective, there are some skill and core courses that must be offered by OTM students. These include keyboarding, shorthand, computer appreciation and application, office management, office practice and entrepreneurship education among others. The technological development in information communication technology has increased the array of opportunities available for people who possess adequate mastery of the knowledge of keyboarding and other ICT skills. By this, keyboarding skills have become one of the important skills required in the world of work as the use of computer has tended to dominate today's business environments. In line with this, Nwabufo (2013) observe that some computer/ICT skills that OTM programme to groom students as global workers include computer skills, skill in instant messaging, e-portfolio, competency in the use of Microsoft words, Microsoft excel, power point, internet skills, word processing, among others.

It has been observed that most of the OTM lecturers were trained in the traditional learning environment mostly with the use of manual typewriters, carbon papers, correcting fluid, typing erasers, stencils and all the likes, including the rigors of calculations and setting involved in tabulation works. Office Technology and Management (OTM) educators are expected to have vast knowledge in the profession. High level of competence is needed from those who impart knowledge to learners to enable these learners to appropriately fit into the society.

There is no doubt that the future of Office Technology and Management as a discipline depends on the competence and readiness of teachers to impart the necessary professional knowledge and skills in the students. The need for OTM teachers to acquire modern office technology skills can, therefore, not be overstressed as this is indispensable if teachers are to impart these skills to the students so that they would be adequately prepared for the demands of the current technological innovations in business offices. OTM teachers are also supposed to be able to apply ICT in teaching and learning of office technology skill courses if they are to adequately deliver instructions to students (Omeje, 2019). Although, Eni (2023) categorized the teachers in the polytechnics into senior and junior, and some polytechnics categorized them into lecturer and instructors, this study considered them lecturers who are saddled with the responsibility of imparting skills and knowledge. For effective delivery of OTM curriculum, therefore, lecturers are expected to possess relevant and adequate ICT-competencies needed to equip OTM graduates to face and surmount the challenges of technologies in modern business environment (Komolafe & Ajani, 2010).

Statement of the Problem

Acquisition of relevant professional skills is critical for OTM students who will adequately fit into the contemporary world of work in office management. The OTM students are supposed to have acquired and competently demonstrate professional skills such as desktop publishing, word processing, webpage design and shorthand writing skills among others. These skills, if acquired by the students before graduating will improve quality of office work and boost economy productivity.

It is however, observed during preliminary investigation that most OTM students seem to be deficient in acquisition of these critical skills. These could be traced to factors such as inadequacy of training facilities and teacher's competence and

proficiency in the identified skills. Although, studies have been conducted on factors influencing professional skills acquisition of tertiary education students, literature is still scarce on how teacher's competence and proficiency can influence skill acquisition of OTM students in public polytechnics in Osun State. Hence the study will investigate the influence of teachers' competence on skill acquisition of Office Technology and Management students in public polytechnics in Osun State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine "influence of teachers' competence on skill acquisition of Office Technology and Management students in public polytechnics in Osun State". Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain OTM teachers' competence in public polytechnics in Osun State.
2. examine the influence of teacher's competence on professional skills acquisition of OTM students in public polytechnics in Osun State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the level of OTM teacher's competence in public polytechnics in Osun State?
2. What is the influence of teacher's competence on professional skills acquisition of OTM students in public polytechnics in Osun State?

Literature Review

Office Technology and Management Programme in Public Polytechnics

Office Technology and Management (OTM) formerly known as Secretarial Studies is an integral part of vocational and technical education where emphasis is placed on acquisition of skills for national development. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) sees technology education, including Office Technology and Management education in the polytechnics, as an aspect of education with the goals of providing course of instructions that will lead to students' acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge needed to perform adequately in the world of work. In other words, the programme is focused on production of manpower that would be self-reliant and contribute to national and manpower development.

According to Esene (2013) the emphasis in the OTM curriculum is to radically shift from where the profession has been in order to join the rest of the developed countries. It was observed that OTM programme is information systems management and information system profession that relates the functions of information system to organizational structure. The OTM curriculum as reviewed by NBTE in 2004 laid emphasis on computer related courses such as (a) secretarial studies and techniques in office management and control (b) information and communication technology application which include computer appreciation like web page design, desktop publishing, database management and (c) general education relating to contemporary issues usually called general studies. The general objectives of the programme can therefore, be summarized as acquisition of secretarial skills, acquisition of general education and laying foundation for advanced studies and for contribution in national development.

Sani (2017) stated that OTM education involves the process of guiding and initiating the learners to acquire the necessary skills, facts, knowledge, habits and attitudes that will make them co-exist with others as useful and productive

members of the society. He upheld that it is a programme of instruction designed to equip its recipients with knowledge and skills for gainful employment. Nwosu (2017) supported this when he said that OTM education is to assist in the production of suitable secretarial manpower with requisite skills, knowledge and attitudes for effective participation in economy. The author opined that OTM education provides adequate training for students for the new world order of technological devices. OTM graduates acquire and develop needed skills, attitudes and knowledge to meet with the new technological challenges which have revolutionary changes in the offices. Ojohwoh (2014) supporting these views said that OTM is an effective, efficient productive and functional educational programme which prepares graduates for self-employment, paid jobs employment, self-reliance and self-realization. It is a competence-based programme that allows its recipients to be independent and be employer of labour.

Competencies Required by Office Technology and Management Teachers for Skills Acquisition in Polytechnics in Osun State

The necessity of teachers possessing required competence for effective and innovative learning cannot be overemphasized. Cabero-Almenara, et al. (2020), opined that teachers must possess ICT-related competencies for effectiveness in the modern ICT-enriched learning environments. Some of these competencies include:

Computer Competencies: This includes ability to use spreadsheets, excel, desktop publishing, Adobe Page maker, CorelDraw/graphics in office automation processing. Ability to understand symbolic language like COBOL, FORTRAN and BASIC and ability to create websites through webpage design (Madu, Obidi & Genevive, 2015).

Communication Competencies: This includes ability to use appropriate telephone techniques, ability to use effective oral communication and ability to compose clear and concise letters, punctuation, capitalization and numerical forms (Dewey, 2009).

Word Processing Competencies: This include understanding the relationship between computer applications and word processing, ability to use different word processing software packages in creating different types of documents; ability to activate the computer and other word processing equipment, input data from original sources speedily and accurately (keyboarding). It also includes: ability to edit, key-in text, spelling checks of texts and so on; ability to merge new mail with old in part or in full by deleting, adding, formatting by copying and pasting texts; ability to format text and display it in acceptable form according to office standards and procedure through tabulations, display, reports, notices, and minutes. Others include ability to proofread documents on the screen before printing; ability to save and retrieve word processing texts when needed and ability to activate the printer and print out copies (Braverman & deCaro, 2019).

Data Processing Competencies: This includes ability to interpret computer printouts; ability to apply basic processing methods including on-line, interacting, real time, batch, centralized and distributed processing; ability to apply principles of recording data, logging in and out and ability to maintain/updating stored databases (Madu, Obidi & Genevive, (2015).

Telecommunication Competencies: This includes ability to send and receive E-mail. Ability to manage mail services (incoming and outgoing mails); ability to fax messages; ability to operate teleconferencing facilities; ability to send and receive messages through computer networks (LAN, WAN, etc.); ability to send and receive correspondence by telex, telephone, mobile phone and private branch exchange and Ability to know modern telecom and their functions (Madu, Obidi & Genevive, 2015).

Planning, Organizing and Decision-Making Competencies: This includes ability to organize workstations for maximum efficiency utilization; ability to supervise work effectively; ability to manage time and task efficiently and ability to accurately interpret material flows, implement procedures and recommend changes in the system (Omeje, 2019).

Reprographic Competencies: This includes ability to save code index and retrieve documents or disks, microfilms and other magnetic media; ability to access files using appropriate techniques such as serial and random access; ability to capture, files creation, files updating, report writing and file inquiry; ability to operate electronic filling, indexing and cataloguing and ability to apply the principle of electronic referencing (Madu, Obidi & Genevive, 2015).

Studies were conducted to investigate teaching competence of teachers in the universities and secondary schools (Esteve-Mon, *et al*, 2020; Sulaiman & Ismail, 2020). Esteve-Mon, *et al* reported that most university teachers seem to have adequate technical digital competence. The relationship between teacher competence and skills acquisition was also found to be robust and positive (Sulaiman & Ismail, 2020). Enang and Okute (2019) considered the importance of leveraging new technologies for skills acquisition in business education and affirm the need for business education teachers to possess necessary skills and competence for managing the e-world. It was noted from the previous studies consulted that, studies investigating teaching competence of polytechnic teachers, especially teachers of Office Technology and Management, are still very scarce. Thus, this study investigated the competencies of OTM teachers in the polytechnics and their influence on professional skill acquisition of the students.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population for the study comprised 27 lecturers of OTM departments of Federal Polytechnic, Ede and Osun State Polytechnic, Iree, Osun State, Nigeria. These tertiary institutions are public polytechnics offering OTM in Osun State. The data for the study were collected through structured questionnaires and were analyzed using simple mean. The population was not too large and therefore the total enumeration was used. The researcher distributed copies of the questionnaire to the respondents in their various offices. The questionnaire consisted of two sections of A and B. Section ‘A’ of the questionnaire sought the demographic data of the respondents, while section ‘B’ contained eighteen (18) items questionnaire which the respondents were requested to indicate their views and opinions on a 4-points scale of ‘Strongly Agree’ = 4 points, ‘Agree’ = 3 points, ‘Disagree’ = 2 points, ‘Strongly Disagree’ = 1 point. All copies of the questionnaire distributed were returned and considered valid. Simple mean measure of central tendency was used to analyse the data collected. Mean score of 2.50 and above were accepted as positive responses while below 2.50 were taken as negative response.

Results

Question 1: What is the level of OTM teacher’s competence in public polytechnics in Osun State?

Table 1: Teacher’s competence in OTM professional skills

S/N	ITEMS	Scores	Mean	Remarks
1.	OTM Teachers have proficiency in CorelDraw	103	3.8	Very high level
2.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Webpage Design	101	3.7	Very high level
3.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Word Processing	92	3.4	High level
4.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Shorthand	92	3.4	High level

5.	OTM teachers have proficiency in PowerPoint presentation	100	3.7	Very high level
6.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Microsoft Excel application	93	3.4	High level
7.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Database Management	99	3.7	Very high level
8.	OTM teachers have proficiency in E-mailing application	101	3.7	Very high level
9.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Video Conferencing System	104	3.8	Very high level
10.	OTM teachers have proficiency in Keyboarding	98	3.6	Very high level
Grand mean			3.6	

Table 1 revealed a grand mean of 3.6 which is rated as “positive” response. This shows that OTM teachers’ competence in word processing, Shorthand, PowerPoint presentation, video conferencing, as well as keyboarding is at a very high level. The table also showed that OTM teachers have high level competence in usage of application software such as CorelDraw, Microsoft Excel application, Database Management and E-mail application.

Question 2: What is the influence of teacher’s competence on skill acquisition of OTM students in public polytechnics in Osun State?

Table 2: Influence of teacher’s competency on skill acquisition of OTM students

S/N	ITEMS	Scores	Mean	Remarks
1.	OTM teachers’ competence in CorelDraw helps students’ skill acquisition in desktop publishing	89	3.3	Positive
2.	OTM teachers’ competence in website design help students’ skill acquisition in Webpage Design	102	3.8	Positive
3.	OTM teachers’ word processing dexterity helps students’ skill acquisition in keyboarding.	101	3.4	Positive
4.	OTM teachers’ shorthand dexterity helps students’ skill acquisition in shorthand	91	3.4	Positive
5.	OTM teachers’ presentation with projector helps students’ skill acquisition in PowerPoint presentation	101	3.7	Positive
6.	OTM teachers’ proficiency in spreadsheet helps students’ skill acquisition in Microsoft Excel application	93	3.4	Positive
7.	OTM teachers’ proficiency in database creation helps students’ skill acquisition in Database Management packages	102	3.8	Positive
8.	OTM teachers’ proficiency in video conferencing helps students’ skill acquisition in video conferencing system	103	3.8	Positive
Grand mean			3.57	

Table 2 revealed a grand mean of 3.57 which is rated as “positive” response. This shows OTM teachers’ proficiency in CorelDraw helps students’ skill acquisition in desktop publishing, proficiency in website design help students’ skill acquisition in Webpage Design, keyboarding dexterity helps students’ skill acquisition in word processing, shorthand dexterity helps students’ skill acquisition in shorthand, presentation with projector helps students’ skill acquisition in PowerPoint presentation, proficiency in spreadsheet helps students’ skill acquisition in Microsoft Excel application, proficiency in database creation helps students’ skill acquisition in Database Management packages, proficiency in database

creation helps students' skill acquisition in Database Management packages and proficiency in video conferencing helps students' skill acquisition in video conferencing system.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the level of professional competencies possessed by OTM teachers in the polytechnics in Osun State, and found it is relatively high. This finding corroborates Esteve-Mon, *et al* (2020) who found that most university teachers seem to have adequate technical digital competence. The finding also showed that the teachers are adequately equipped with necessary competence for effective impartation of knowledge as skills as opined by Cabero-Almenara, *et al.* (2020) that teachers must possess ICT-related competencies for effectiveness in the modern ICT-enriched learning environments.

The study also found that teachers' competence can positively influence professional skills acquisition of the students. This agrees with Sulaiman and Ismail, (2020) that the relationship between teacher competence and skills acquisition was robust and positive. It also confirms Cabero-Almenara, *et al.* that teachers who possessed ICT-related competencies will be effective in the modern ICT-enriched learning environments. The implication of this finding is that apart from teachers' competencies, there might be other factors, like adequacy of instructional facilities, responsible for the professional skills acquisition of OTM students which might need further investigation.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the level of OTM lecturers' competence in teaching OTM professional skills in public polytechnics in Osun State is relatively high. It could also be implied from the findings that the competency level of OTM lecturers is enough to teach the required OTM professional skills. It was further concluded that lecturers' competence has influence on professional skills acquisition even though.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Management of the public polytechnics should ensure provision of adequate instructional facilities necessary for professional skills acquisition since teachers' competence is on high level.
2. OTM lecturers should explore other factors affecting professional skills acquisition of their students with a view to ensuring provision of high-quality products of the OTM programme.

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